

Integration of a Informatics Teaching-Learning Laboratory into Pre-Service Informatics Teacher Education

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Abstract

In order to understand the digital world and the underlying concepts of digital devices and applications, one of the skills required is algorithmic thinking. Therefore, it is important that not only the students learn algorithmic thinking in school, but also future informatics teachers. To enable them to experience this as effectively as possible, factors such as TPACK competencies and self-efficacy are important. This poster presents a study design on how a teaching-learning lab (TLL) can be integrated into pre-service informatics teacher education. The goal is, on the one hand, to increase the future teachers TPACK competencies and self-efficacy, and, on the other hand, to develop two different didactic approaches that foster pupils' algorithmic thinking. Considering this, a Robotic workshop with a block-based programming language was developed integrating these didactic approaches, both of which are designed to promote pupils' algorithmic thinking. The students conducted these two workshops in our TLL and reflected on their didactic activities. Using a mixed-methods approach, we analyzed how students' TPACK skills and self-efficacy develop over time and how two different didactic approaches differ in terms of promoting algorithmic thinking in pupils. In the next step further data will be collected, evaluated and analyzed to achieve more insights to this preliminary results.

Keywords

Algorithmic Thinking, Computational Thinking, Block-based programming

1. Introduction

It is undoubtedly important that today's students learn to use digital tools and devices in a self-directed way. Moreover, in our digital-driven world, knowledge of computer science and digital orientation is required to understand its complexity. Therefore, competencies in computational thinking (CT) are required. Among various definitions, CT is also the ability to design algorithms and interact with the digitized world based on computer science skills [1, 2, 3, 4]. In [5] algorithmic thinking is defined as the ability to create and understand algorithms. In practice this means to be able to analyze and specify a problem, to know the rules of solving a problem as well as to design an algorithm and further improve it to be more

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efficient [5]. The instructional learning environment needs to be aligned with the learners' needs. They need to be supported in such a way through the learning environment that they can acquire these computational skills. At the same time, pre-service teachers need training in self-reflection, self-efficacy, and TPACK competencies [6] to teach algorithmic thinking to future pupils. This poster presents the study design in which, on the one hand, the development of TPACK competencies (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) [6] and the self-efficacy of students attending a TLL-seminar are investigated. Students conduct various workshops at school classes in the TLL during the semester and repeatedly reflect on their didactic activities. On the other hand, two different didactic approaches (see Figure 1) of a Robotic workshop with a block-based programming language, both of which are intended to promote algorithmic thinking of the pupils, are evaluated within the study. The study follows the mixed-method design.

2. Study Design

2.1. Integration of the Teaching Learning Laboratory in a seminar

N = 4 students of informatics attended a didactics seminar in which they gave Robotic workshops with the teaching-learning laboratory (TLL) visiting school classes in which they were videotaped. During the semester, the students reflected on their teaching skills based on these video recordings. At the end of the semester, they were surveyed regarding their development of TPACK competencies [6] as well as self-efficacy using Post-then-Pre-questionnaires.

2.2. Robotic Workshop Design

We developed one workshop with two didactical structures that are intended to promote pupils algorithmic thinking, see Figure 1:

A: SWAT concept [7]: a guided problem-oriented approach, following a semantic wave [8]

B: CPB concept: a constructionist problem-based approach [9, 10]

In both didactical structures pupils work on problems using Robots and a block-based programming language.

Figure 1 shows the almost identical but structured differently in terms of methodology topics of the workshops: The didactical structure A, which is based on our developed guided problem-based SWAT concept [7], methodically follows a semantic wave in each module and is described here in more detail [11]. The order of the topics is also shown in Figure 1 and the problems are guided in the sense that they are broken down into sub-problems which the pupils then have to solve independently. The second structure is an constructionist problem-based concept [9, 10] in which the first module provides the pupils with all the relevant knowledge information (knowledge base) they need to be able to solve modules 2-4 independently and can chose the order of the modules freely. The workshop is conducted with pupils who are in 8th or 9th grade of a secondary school.

<p>Didactical Structure A: SWAT concept using a semantic wave</p>	<p>Module No. 1: Disco The robot should drive a programmed choreography accompanied by LED outputs. (moving action, LED-Display)</p>			
<p>Didactical Structure B: constructionist problem-based concept</p>	<p>Module No. 1: Knowledge base The necessary knowledge for the other 3 modules is conveyed without anticipating the problems of the coming modules.</p>			

Figure 1: Robotic workshop with two didactical structures in comparison: SWAT concept [7] using a semantic wave [8] and Constructionist problem-based concept [9, 10].

2.3. Method and Instruments

In order to assess students' TPACK competences and self-efficacy on the one hand and, on the other hand pupils' competence in algorithmic thinking, we investigate the following research questions (RQ):

RQ1: How can pre-service teacher's TPACK competencies and self-efficacy be developed?

RQ2: To what extent can pupils' algorithmic thinking be developed through different workshop settings?

The research questions are addressed in a mixed-method approach and will be examined with the following instruments (IRQ): *IRQ1:* Questionnaire for the TPACK-competencies and the self-efficacy in a retrospective Post-Then-Pre-questionnaire design and a qualitative descriptive analysis. *IRQ2:* Pupils' worksheets and created programs evaluating with the help of a reductive, qualitative content analysis according to the interpretative paradigm of [12] using a developed category system (qualitative analysis); valid Algorithmic Thinking Test [13] (pre-posttest with control group) analyzing by using the approximate adjusted fractional Bayes factors for testing informative hypotheses [14] (quantitative analysis).

3. Summary

In this poster, we present our integration of the Informatics TLL into the education of pre-service teachers. It is a novel concept to integrate a TLL into teaching, where on the one hand pupils come to learn the core competence algorithmic thinking and, on the other hand, students can gain didactical hands-on experience already during the studies and not only in the traineeships. Feedback analyses allow for extensive student self-reflection during the semester. In addition, the development of TPACK competencies related to informatics teaching as well as students' self-efficacy are evaluated and assessed through self-assessment. Finally, the two didactical structures are also investigated in terms of teaching algorithmic thinking to pupils. In a next step, more data will now be collected, as N = 4 students is a small number of students so far, and then be evaluated.

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